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CASE SERIES

Therapeutic Performance of Combined Therapies in the Management of Recent Acne Scars: A Case Series

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Abstract

Introduction: The management of acne scars represents a therapeutic challenge due to the variability in scar types and resistance to conventional treatments. This report describes a case series in which personalized combined treatment protocols were used to address acne scars, employing technologies such as fractional CO laser, microneedling fractional radiofrequency, microneedling with PRP, and intense pulsed light (IPL). This multifaceted approach aims to optimize clinical outcomes while minimizing recovery time.

Main Symptoms and Clinical Findings: Patients presented with atrophic and/or hypertrophic acne scars primarily distributed on the face, with varying severity of post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation and a history of severe acne.

Diagnosis, Therapeutic Interventions, and Outcomes: Individualized treatment protocols combining laser, radiofrequency, microneedling, and PRP were implemented. Over 180-210 days of follow-up, significant improvements in skin texture and scar reduction were documented, with notable decreases in severity scores (ECCA scale) and pigmentation (PAHPI scale). Treatments were well tolerated, with minimal discomfort reported by patients.

Conclusion: This personalized, combined treatment approach for acne scars proved effective in improving clinical outcomes within a shorter timeframe. The findings suggest that individualized protocols may be superior to conventional treatments, highlighting the importance of tailoring strategies to the specific characteristics of each patient.

Introduction:

Acne, a chronic inflammatory skin disease with high global prevalence, primarily affects adolescents and young adults and is often associated with permanent scarring that can impair patients' quality of life. Acne scars, both atrophic and hypertrophic, pose a complex clinical challenge due to their resistance to conventional treatments and their potential to worsen over time, especially in the presence of factors such as aging and photodamage. Current literature suggests that while numerous interventions exist for the treatment of acne and its sequelae, no single therapeutic approach has consistently demonstrated effectiveness across all scar types or patient profiles (1,2).

Traditionally, the management of acne scars has relied on standardized protocols and conventional therapies, which often fail to fully address the specific needs of each patient. This generalized approach can limit clinical outcomes, prolong recovery times, and even increase the difficulty of treating scars in the long term. Thus, a significant gap in knowledge and clinical practice has emerged, necessitating a more individualized and multifaceted therapeutic approach to improve patient outcomes (3,4).

In response to this need, we propose that a personalized therapeutic strategy, based on the combination of innovative technologies and treatments, can optimize clinical outcomes and shorten recovery times in patients with acne scars. This hypothesis is grounded in the potential synergy between different techniques, such as fractional CO laser, fractional radiofrequency, intense pulsed light, and drug delivery methods using platelet-rich plasma or hyaluronic acid compounds. These

modalities, when applied in a personalized manner, can more effectively address the morphological and physiological characteristics of each patient's scars, achieving greater therapeutic precision and minimizing adverse effects (5).

In this context, the present study aims to evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of a combined protocol of individualized treatments for acne scars using a case series design. By applying specific combinations of techniques based on each patient's scar morphology and characteristics, we seek not only to enhance clinical outcomes but also to identify the factors that optimize skin response and accelerate the recovery process. Outcomes will be assessed using validated clinical scales to measure scar severity and post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation, providing objective data on the effectiveness of this approach.

Case Presentation:

Case 1:

A 23-year-old male patient with Fitzpatrick skin type IV reported a history of severe acne lasting one year, which left scarring on his face. The patient denied having received prior dermatological treatments for his scars and reported no personal or family history of relevant conditions that could affect treatment. No psychosocial factors were identified that might interfere with treatment adherence.

Clinical

Physical examination revealed multiple atrophic scars, including ice pick and rolling types, predominantly distributed on the cheeks, forehead, and bilateral temporal regions. The scars were observed to be deep and long-standing, which limited short-term expectations for outcomes but allowed for the implementation of an intensive treatment protocol.

Diagnostic Assessment:

To quantify scar severity, the *Echelle d'Évaluation Clinique des Cicatrices d'Acné* (ECCA) scale was employed, yielding an initial score of 240, indicative of significant severity. Additionally, the PAHPI scale for post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation was used, with an initial score of 6. These baseline measurements provided objective markers to evaluate clinical progress and the efficacy of the therapy over time.

Therapeutic

The treatment was structured in phases and combined multiple procedures to achieve comprehensive improvement and accelerate recovery. The strategy included the following:

Intervention:

• Initial Preparation and Microneedling with PRP:

The intervention began with spot application of 90% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) to ice pick scars. Following thorough asepsis and antisepsis with chlorhexidine, a session of microneedling was performed using the Dermapen device equipped with 12 needles. The depth was adjusted to 0.5 mm for the forehead and 1.0 mm for the cheeks and chin, with a speed setting of level 2. During the microneedling procedure, 3 cc of PRP, previously extracted via centrifugation of the patient's blood, was applied to maximize plasma penetration in the treated areas, promoting an anti-inflammatory response and enhancing collagen regeneration.

• Fractional Radiofrequency with Microneedles and Q-Switched ND:YAG Laser:

Upon observing the development of post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation in areas treated with TCA, the Q-Switched ND:YAG laser was incorporated into the protocol, delivered in three monthly sessions to reduce hyperpigmentation. The laser parameters were adjusted for darker skin types, employing three passes with specific configurations: the first at 585 nm with a 2 mm spot and a fluence of 2.3 J/cm², and the second and third passes at 1064 nm. The final pass was delivered in fractional mode using spots of 7 mm and 15 mm with fluences of 2.0 J/cm² and 1.0 J/cm², respectively.

Fractional radiofrequency was applied in the same session to improve skin texture and quality, using the FIXER DV9 device set to two depths (3.5 mm for cheeks and 2.2 mm for the entire face), with intensities adjusted according to the area treated. This procedure was repeated monthly to maximize collagen remodeling.

Supportive Therapy and Post-Procedure Care:

After each session, a skin repair cream containing the Charlotte Meiers cellular complex and a mineral sunscreen were applied to minimize additional damage from sun exposure. Additionally, a layer of cold aloe vera gel was used immediately after laser and radiofrequency procedures to reduce acute inflammation.

Follow-Up and Results:

Clinical follow-up was conducted over 180 days, with periodic assessments and photographic documentation. The ECCA scale demonstrated progressive improvement, reaching a final score of 80, indicating a significant reduction in scar appearance. Regarding post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation, the PAHPI scale showed no significant change, maintaining a final score of 6, similar to the baseline, after the intervention with the Q-Switched laser. The combination of treatments was well tolerated by the patient, who reported minimal discomfort and good adherence to the home care protocol (see Table 1 and Figure 1).

Case

2:

A 20-year-old male patient with a history of acne since the age of 15, which had exacerbated in the past three months. This period was characterized by inflammatory outbreaks, predominantly with painful nodules on the face, resulting in atrophic and hypertrophic scars on the cheeks and forehead. The patient had previously been treated with doxycycline, which yielded no significant improvement, and isotretinoin, which was discontinued after four months due to sustained triglyceride elevations reaching three times the normal limit. The patient reported no relevant medical or family history.

Clinical

Findings:

Initial physical examination revealed multiple open and closed comedones, along with more than 20 erythematous papules and painful nodules that evolved into atrophic scars (ice pick and boxcar types) on the cheeks and forehead, as well as hypertrophic scars in some areas. Initial evaluation of scar severity was quantified using the ECCA scale (*Échelle d'évaluation clinique des cicatrices d'acné*), with a score of 320, and the PAHPI (*Postacne Hyperpigmentation Index*), which recorded an initial score of 16.

Timeline (see Table 2):

- **Days 1–120:** Treatment with isotretinoin was initiated but discontinued due to persistent hyperlipidemia.
- **Days 120–210:** A combined treatment protocol was implemented, including fractional microneedling radiofrequency, fractional CO laser, and PRP drug delivery.
- **Day 210:** Final evaluation revealed a reduction in the ECCA score to 175 and the PAHPI score to 11.

Diagnostic Assessment:

The evaluation included a detailed physical examination and the application of severity scales to objectively quantify scar evolution. The ECCA and PAHPI scales provided a rigorous comparative analysis of changes in skin texture and post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation, ensuring quantitative reliability in outcome assessment.

Therapeutic

Intervention:

Following the discontinuation of isotretinoin, a therapeutic protocol combining the following was initiated:

- **Fractional Microneedling Radiofrequency:**
Two passes were performed per session, adjusting depth and energy based on the scar location and type. For the first pass (cheeks), radiofrequency levels of 6-4 were used, with frequencies of 1 MHz and penetration depths of 3.5 to 2.8 mm. The second pass covered the entire face, with depths adjusted to 2.2 to 1.4 mm.
- **Fractional CO Laser:**
Two passes were applied. The first used a 100 mm surgical handpiece for boxcar scars in super-pulse mode, with 50 mJ energy and a pulse duration of 1.6 ms. The second pass targeted the entire face using a fractional handpiece, adjusting density levels to enhance the treatment of rolling scars.
- **PRP Drug Delivery:**
After laser and radiofrequency treatments, 3 cc of PRP was applied using a drug delivery technique to enhance the penetration of growth factors in treated areas, optimizing dermal regeneration.
- **LED Phototherapy:**
Red LED light at 660 nm with 60% irradiance was used for 15 minutes to promote cellular regeneration and minimize post-procedure inflammatory response.

This protocol was repeated in three monthly sessions. Post-procedure care included the application of a repair complex and mineral sunscreen to protect and soothe treated skin.

Follow-Up**and****Results:**

At the end of the intervention (Day 210), the patient exhibited a notable reduction in scar severity, with the ECCA score decreasing from 320 to 175 and the PAHPI score from 16 to 11. Clinically, there was significant improvement in skin texture and thickness, with visible reduction of atrophic scars and attenuation of post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation. No severe complications or permanent adverse effects were reported, although the patient experienced mild transient erythema and edema, which resolved within 72 hours post-procedure (see Table 2 and Figure 2).

Case 3:

A 24-year-old female patient with a prior diagnosis of PCOS under evaluation due to hypertrichosis and menstrual irregularities presented with concerns about a recent outbreak of comedonal acne predominantly affecting the cheeks. Initial evaluation revealed multiple open and closed comedones, over 20 erythematous papules, and atrophic scars primarily on the cheeks and forehead, some of which were erythematous. The patient reported no prior treatment for acne scars and no relevant family history of severe acne.

Clinical**Findings:**

Physical examination revealed comedonal acne lesions and erythematous papules, predominantly on the cheeks. The scars were characterized as atrophic and erythematous, with a distribution focused on the cheeks and forehead. The clinical diagnosis was moderate papulopustular acne with a strong comedonal component, accompanied by atrophic scars and post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation.

Timeline of Therapeutic Interventions and Outcomes (see Table 3 and Figure 3):

- **Day 0:** Oral isotretinoin at 20 mg daily was initiated to address the active acne. A facial care routine for oily skin was implemented, including a gentle cleanser, non-comedogenic moisturizer, and broad-spectrum sunscreen.
- **Day 30:** Treatment for sequelae began with intense pulsed light (IPL) tailored for acne and pigmentation, using parameters adjusted for the patient's skin type and lesion status.
- **Day 120:** Partial improvement in acne and initial reduction in pigmented lesions were noted. Fractional microneedling radiofrequency and CO laser were initiated to treat atrophic scars. Drug delivery with NCTF, containing hyaluronic acid and a complex of vitamins and amino acids, was incorporated to enhance dermal revitalization and regeneration.
- **Day 210:** At the conclusion of the treatment protocol, the patient showed notable improvement in scars and hyperpigmentation, along with enhanced overall skin quality and tone.

Diagnostic Evaluation:

To quantify the initial severity and post-treatment changes, validated scales were employed: the ECCA scale for scar severity and the PAHPI scale for post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation. Results demonstrated a reduction in the ECCA score from 55 to 15 and in the PAHPI score from 12 to 6, indicating a favorable clinical response.

Therapeutic**Interventions:**

The patient underwent a combined treatment protocol aimed at achieving comprehensive and sustained improvement in acne sequelae:

- **Oral Isotretinoin:** Administered at 20 mg/day, accompanied by an oral contraceptive (Bellaface) for hormonal management and teratogenic prevention. This treatment helped reduce the inflammatory component of active acne.
- **Intense Pulsed Light (IPL):** Three IPL sessions were performed using a Korean FracLight device, with parameters adjusted to treat both inflammatory lesions and residual hyperpigmentation. Passes included an acne-specific program at 640 nm and a vascular program at 560 nm to address persistent erythema in scars.
- **Fractional Microneedling Radiofrequency (RF):** Fractional RF was applied at various depths using the FIXER DV9 device, allowing controlled penetration to stimulate collagen remodeling in areas with deeper scars.

- **CO Laser:** In the final phase, CO laser sessions were performed with fractional passes and specific surgical handpieces for boxcar scars. Depth and density were adjusted according to scar type and the patient's tolerance.
- **Drug Delivery with NCTF:** After laser treatments, the NCTF complex containing hyaluronic acid and dermal revitalization factors was applied using drug delivery techniques. This procedure improved hydration and skin density, promoting increased collagen production.

Follow-Up and Efficacy Results:

The multimodal treatment produced clinically significant results. The ECCA scale showed a substantial reduction from 55 to 15, while the PAHPI scale demonstrated improvement in hyperpigmentation, decreasing from 12 to 6. The patient tolerated the treatments well, experiencing minimal irritation and no significant adverse effects. Progressive improvements were observed in skin quality, with a reduction in atrophic scars and a more even tone.

Discussion:

This case series evaluated a combined and individualized treatment protocol for acne scars, integrating technologies such as fractional CO laser, fractional microneedling radiofrequency, intense pulsed light (IPL), and microneedling with platelet-rich plasma (PRP) or the revitalizing complex NCTF. The results demonstrate that this personalized approach facilitates significant improvements in skin texture, reduction of post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation, and substantial decreases in scar severity as measured by the ECCA and PAHPI scales. The intervention was well tolerated by patients, with no permanent adverse effects reported, suggesting that this combination of techniques may offer superior benefits compared to conventional treatments.

Recent literature supports and complements these findings on the effectiveness of treatments such as fractional CO laser and fractional radiofrequency for atrophic acne scars. Various studies indicate that fractional CO laser is highly effective in collagen remodeling and scar depth reduction. For instance, one study found that this modality achieved significant improvement in 50.4% of patients after one session, particularly for rolling scars compared to ice pick scars (6). Another study reported that the combined use of fractional CO laser and radiofrequency yields better results with fewer sessions and a reduced risk of adverse effects (7).

Regarding the use of PRP in combination with microneedling, opinions are divided. While some studies suggest that PRP can accelerate dermal regeneration and enhance outcomes for complex scars, others have not found statistically significant improvements compared to microneedling alone (8). However, our findings align with literature indicating that PRP may enhance the early phase of tissue repair and offer additional benefits for deep or long-standing scars.

There are discrepancies in the additional efficacy of PRP combined with microneedling. Some studies report accelerated dermal regeneration and scar reduction, while others find no statistically significant differences compared to microneedling alone. Our findings suggest that PRP may enhance the initial phase of tissue repair and clinical outcomes, particularly for complex, long-standing scars, as observed in Case 1. Nevertheless, the precise effects of PRP and its interaction with other treatments remain an active area of research and require larger, controlled studies to establish its role in combined protocols.

Limitations:

The limitations of this study include a small sample size and the absence of a control group, which restrict the generalizability of the results and the ability to attribute changes solely to the intervention. Additionally, the follow-up period was limited, preventing an assessment of the long-term stability of the outcomes. Despite these limitations, the personalized and multimodal approach is a notable strength of the study, reflecting a treatment paradigm tailored to the morphological and physiological characteristics of scars and the patient's skin type. This approach not only achieves significant improvements in less time but also provides an alternative to standardized treatments, which often fail to adapt to individual variability, perpetuating scars that become more resistant to treatment.

The findings of this study highlight the need for an individualized and multidimensional approach to treating acne scars. The combination of technologies and therapies should be adapted to each patient, addressing both the scar type and their response at each treatment phase. This personalized protocol not only optimizes clinical outcomes but also minimizes recovery time. In clinical practice, this approach encourages re-evaluating standardized protocols, which, while convenient, may exacerbate the chronicity and resistance of scars. For research, it is crucial to develop controlled studies with larger sample sizes to better define therapeutic combinations and

their specific indications. Additionally, long-term follow-up is recommended to evaluate the durability of results achieved with these multimodal protocols.

Conclusions:

This case series provides evidence that a personalized and combined therapeutic protocol can be an effective strategy for treating acne sequelae, offering superior outcomes compared to conventional treatments, which often fail to adapt to individual needs. The integration of technologies such as fractional CO laser, fractional radiofrequency, IPL, and microneedling with PRP allows for addressing the specific characteristics of each patient, optimizing the quality of outcomes and reducing improvement time. This approach emphasizes that there is no “one-size-fits-all” formula for treating acne scars; rather, individualization and technique combination seem to be key to overcoming the limitations of traditional treatments and significantly improving clinical outcomes.

Patient Perspective:

Patients reported satisfaction with the results and emphasized the importance of seeing early improvements in their scars and skin quality, which increased their adherence to treatment and commitment to self-care.

Informed Consent:

Patients provided informed consent for the use of their information in this study.

Data availability

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